

Simplified Modelling for the Seismic Performance Assessment of Automated Rack-Supported Warehouses

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Abstract

A reduced-order modeling approach is proposed for the linear and nonlinear analysis of Automated Rack-Supported Warehouse (ARSW) structures under seismic loads. Steel ARSWs are massive structures that employ traditional racking configurations to support both the stored pallets and the external cladding shell. Capturing all the structural details of an ARSW requires tens or hundreds of thousands of elements, leading to complex numerical models that are analyzed with difficulty even in the linear range and are clearly unsuitable for nonlinear analysis. Thus, despite being prolific in earthquake-prone areas, their true seismic behaviour remains largely untested. As a viable compromise between fidelity and low computational cost, we offer instead a reduced-order model that relies on the substitution of the one or more built-up columns (i.e. upright frames) with equivalent Timoshenko beam-column elements and two-node link elements. The resulting model can support both 2D and 3D elastic and inelastic analyses, offering a powerful tool for the seismic assessment of ARSWs and of complex structures comprising built-up columns in general.

Introduction

Arising from the need of easy assembly, adjustable geometry and low cost, steel Pallet Racking Systems (PRSs) exhibit a number of peculiarities that distinguish them from ordinary building structures. A typical PRS configuration consists of two directions, the down-aisle, which is used by the forklift trucks in order to deposit and withdraw the goods and, perpendicularly, the cross-aisle (Figure 1). The columns, called uprights, are continuously perforated to accommodate the pallet beams, with their connection being neither bolted nor welded, but hooked, leading to a flexible moment resisting frame in the down-aisle direction. In order to secure lateral stability in cross-aisle, the uprights are connected by bracing members typically with one bolt at each end, creating a so-called upright frame. Unlike typical buildings, the weight of these steel members is only a small fraction, e.g. 5-10%, of the live loads. For these reasons, their design is not based on codes for regular steel structures, e.g. EN1993 [1] (Eurocode 3), but on special standards, such as EN 15512 [2] in Europe, ANSI MH 16.1 [3] in the US or AS 4084 [4] in Australia. These specifications call for design assisted by testing to acknowledge that the response of members and joints to loading cannot be covered exclusively by numerical analysis.

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As a result of their loose connections and lightness, PRSs are flexible structures, characterized by significant geometric nonlinearities and local buckling phenomena. Thus, in seismic-prone areas a vertical bracing system along with horizontal braces is used down-aisle, enhancing the stiffness of the rack and limiting the development of soft story collapse mechanisms. The seismic behaviour of braced and unbraced PRSs was investigated during the European research projects SEISRACKS [5] and SEISRACKS2 [6] by means of experimental and numerical tests ([7], [8] and [9]). The full-scale tests revealed the sensitivity of racks to construction details and to system-level effects not completely detected during the code-mandated component and subassembly tests.

Figure 1: Plan and side views of a typical PRS. Two directions are defined, the down-aisle which is used by the forklift trucks and, perpendicularly, the cross-aisle.

The increasing demand for space savings and automation raises the necessity for warehouses storing more pallets over the same footprint, thus increasing the height. Conventional PRSs cannot be straightforwardly extended in the vertical direction as the upright frames behave as cantilevers and thus their critical buckling load is low. As a result, over the past few years, manufacturers prefer to connect the upright frames by a roofing system, comprising roof trusses along the cross-aisle direction together with purlins (Figure 5) and light secondary beams along the down-aisle, avoiding the construction of an independent external shell-support structure. Additional braced bays, the so-called bracing towers (see for example case study 1, Figure 14), may also be added at regular intervals along the down-aisle direction to add strength and stiffness, while the roof truss and secondary beams at the roof and the pallet loading levels provide load transfer along their axis. These clad rack warehouses often provide an automated management system for pallet storage and retrieval using integrated artificial intelligence and robotics, referred to as Automated Rack-Supported Warehouses (ARSW). Two main types can be distinguished based on their configuration and handling system, namely the automated double-depth cranes (Figure 2) and the automated multi-depth shuttles (Figure 3). Double-depth cranes belong to direct-access systems and provide easy accessibility to the pallets, stored with a maximum number of two units for each row in the

cross-aisle direction, but decrease the use of the available footprint of the warehouse by needing more aisles. On the other hand, multi-depth shuttles are more compact systems and maximize the storage density, while losing accessibility to the pallets that are stored in long storage tunnels serviced by mechanized shuttles running on rails (Figure 4).

At present, ARSWs are usually built with the same or similar cold formed profiles used for conventional PRSs although their dimensions and structural behaviour are very different. Moreover, there is no official reference document specific for the design of ARSWs; designers are obliged to rely on EN16681 [10] and other PRS standards for seismic design. The aforementioned uncertainties may increase their vulnerability in extreme load scenarios, such as high wind speeds and seismic actions. This was also highlighted during the Emilia-Romagna earthquake (Figure 6), where several ARSWs were severely damaged or even collapsed. Given the above observations, there is presently significant interest in achieving some improved ductility for ARSWs by forming at least a limited plastic failure mechanism where yielding may spread from element to element rather than lead to sudden progressive collapse.

Figure 2: Example of a double-depth ARSW in the construction stage showing the Z-braced upright frames of the cross-aisle direction (photo courtesy of SACMA S.p.a).

Figure 3: Example of a multi-depth ARSW in the construction stage showing the K-braced upright frames along the cross-aisle direction (photo courtesy of SACMA S.p.a).

Figure 4: In the multi-depth systems, pallets are handled by mechanized shuttles running on rail beams along the cross-aisle direction. The rail and pallet beams form horizontal grids of beams, enhancing the stiffness of the structure (photo courtesy of Ferretto Group).

Figure 5: Structural configuration of the upright frame-to-roof bolted connection in the cross-aisle direction.

Nowadays, seismic performance assessment (EN1998-3 [12], ASCE41-13 [13]) is based on extensive numerical analyses via nonlinear static or dynamic approaches. A typical finite-element model of a modern ARSW comprises hundreds of thousands of nodes and elements with nearly a million of degrees of freedom (DOFs), rendering the nonlinear simulation of the whole structure practically infeasible. Even during the design, where the analyses are linear elastic, simplifications are accepted in terms of accuracy by considering a portion of the structure or relying on two-dimensional models, as the design verifications that the software has to perform on a full 3D model may take days or even weeks. Striking the need for a balance between simplicity and accuracy is even more dire for nonlinear analyses where convergence is hampered by model size. Herein, a simplified modelling approach is introduced that is based on the substitution of the upright frames with equivalent Timoshenko beam elements. Test cases for double- and multi-depth ARSWs are presented using both two- and three-dimensional models, showing the results of linear and nonlinear analyses with different element models.

Figure 6: Collapse of the Sant'Agostino Ceramics warehouse near Sant' Agostino village. Emilia-Romagna earthquake 2012 [11].

Modelling of racking systems

Background

The modelling of steel racks is a challenging problem as it requires capturing the dynamic response of thin-walled perforated members and their semi-rigid connections. In order to simulate appropriately all possible failure mechanisms, a three-dimensional numerical model with shell and solid finite elements is required. However, from the engineering point of view, this practice is seldom followed for design, as the computational time is prohibitively expensive. Thus, a conventional beam element model is frequently used, calibrated to a small number of static and cyclic experimental and possibly additional numerical analyses.

Static tests are needed to determine the ultimate capacity load and elastic stiffness of the structural components of the rack. As the uprights are made of thin-walled open sections, they are prone to a number of buckling modes. Local buckling resistance, vastly deteriorated by the presence of perforations, can be calculated by stub-column compression tests and it is taken into account by adopting a reduced “effective” cross-section area during the verification checks. Depending on the thickness-to-braced-length ratio, uprights may also exhibit distortional or flexural buckling or a combination of the two. Buckling curves that account for such effects specific to uprights have been proposed by Elias et al. [14] and Miranda et al. [15].

The transverse shear stiffness of the upright frame also has a significant impact on the behaviour of the rack structure in the cross-aisle direction. As pointed by Talebian et al. [16] there are various factors influencing the transverse shear deformation of the frames, mostly related to the deformation of the braces and their ends, as well as slipping and bending of the bolts. In a beam-column element model this phenomenon can be implicitly taken into account by introducing partial axial end-releases in the bracing beam elements or using a cross-section area reduction factor, which can be of a magnitude of 5%.

Less frequently, quasi-static cyclic tests are conducted, mainly to determine the moment-rotation curves for beam-to-column rack joints. The hysteretic response of this connection influences the capability of the rack to absorb plastic deformations (or dissipate energy in Eurocode parlance) in the down-aisle direction and is characterized by slippage, pinching and stiffness-degrading behaviour [17]. Improved performance can be achieved in terms of bearing capacity and rotation deformability by introducing additional bolts (and welds) in the connection, as observed in [18]. Further considerations are the effect of pallet sliding and viscous damping, which have been captured by shake table tests ([19], [20]).

Proposed Simplified Model

As current ARSW codes do not strictly enforce capacity design rules, brittle failure mechanisms are not prevented, and the redistribution of stresses is inherently limited for realistic designs. Thus, an elastic material model can often be employed. On the other hand, geometric nonlinearities cannot be easily disregarded due to the non-negligible lateral flexibility.

Therefore, the idea of substituting built-up columns with single equivalent elastic elements has found good use in literature. For example, Belleri et al [21] employed equivalent beam elements in tandem with simple springs for the elastic linear seismic design of industrial buildings. Kalochairetis [22] employed elastic Timoshenko beam-column elements to determine the buckling capacity of laced built-up columns and performed various test cases investigating the effect of imperfections. Building upon such concepts, which have not been applied so far for cold-formed racking elements, we propose a linear Timoshenko beam

model to replace built-up columns when material nonlinearity is not an issue, as well as a nonlinear two-node link element (OpenSees' [23]) to incorporate material inelasticity for investigating more ductile designs. In the latter case, novel nonlinear Timoshenko beam elements can offer alternative modelling solutions ([24], [25]). The target is to offer a flexible approach for quantifying the seismic performance of PRS structures, especially of multi- and double-depth ARSWs. Furthermore, we propose employing each such equivalent element to represent more than one upright frame at a time to further reduce the number of DOFs.

To substitute a single upright frame with an equivalent beam-column or two-node link element, first a transformation to a Timoshenko beam has to be performed. Its equivalent cross-section is composed of N upright sections, each having A_i area and d_i distance from the mass centre. Using Steiner's rule, the equivalent cross-section area A_{eq} and moment of inertia I_{eq} can be approximated as:

$$A_{eq} = \sum_{i=1}^N A_i \quad (1)$$

$$I_{eq} = \sum_{i=1}^N A_i d_i^2 \quad (2)$$

Table 1: Cross-section shear area for bracing patterns D, Z, K and X per EN1993-1-1 [26]

D-bracing	Z-bracing	K-bracing	X-bracing
$A_s = \frac{EA_d}{G} \frac{h_0^2 a}{d^3}$	$A_s = \frac{EA_d}{G} \frac{h_0^2 a}{d^3} \frac{1}{1 + \frac{h_0^3}{d^3} \frac{A_d}{A_h}}$	$A_s = \frac{EA_d}{G} \frac{h_0^2 a}{d^3}$	$A_s = 2 \frac{EA_d}{G} \frac{h_0^2 a}{d^3}$

While A_{eq} and I_{eq} can fully capture Euler-Bernoulli-beam bending, the equivalent shear area $A_{s,eq}$ is required to introduce additional Timoshenko-beam shear deformations. Essentially it captures the deformation of the bracing elements and their connections and thus depends on the geometry and typology of the bracing system. For common bracing patterns (e.g. D, Z, K and X) with constant cross-sections and geometry along the height, closed-form solutions may be derived by considering a segment of the upright frame and enforcing static equilibrium. Such expressions are also available in the literature [26], as shown in Table 1. To account for the axial flexibility of the end connections of upright frame diagonals, an equivalent cross-sectional area is typically used, considering that the diagonal and its partial release act as springs in series:

$$\frac{EA_{d,eq}}{L} = \frac{K_d K_{p.release}}{K_d + K_{p.release}}, \quad (3)$$

where $K_d = EA_d/L$, while A_d and $A_{d,eq}$ are the actual and the equivalent cross-sectional area of the diagonal, respectively. Subsequently, the shear area of the equivalent column is calculated using the formulae of Table 1 with A_d replaced by $A_{d,eq}$.

For systems with non-constant bracing sections and varying spacing along the height, an approximate procedure can be followed instead:

1. Separate the upright frame of interest and calculate its I_{eq} from Eq. (2).
2. Create a cantilever test by applying pinned releases to the nodes at the bottom and point loads on the top. The sum of nodal loads P_{tot} and corresponding roof displacement δ_{tot} are related as:

$$P_{tot} = \frac{12}{4 + \Phi} \frac{EI_{eq}}{L^3} \delta_{tot}, \quad (4)$$

where $\Phi = \frac{12EI_{eq}}{GA_{s,eq}L^2}$ and L the length of the upright frame.

3. Solving Eq. (4) for the approximated $\bar{A}_{s,eq}$ yields:

$$\bar{A}_{s,eq} = \frac{E}{G} \frac{P_{tot} (3I_{eq}) L}{(3EI_{eq}) \delta_{tot} - P_{tot} L^3} \quad (5)$$

For elastic material models, this information is sufficient for generating the equivalent beam-column elements. On the other hand, this approach is not adequate for a nonlinear model, as the shear properties of most Timoshenko beam-column elements are essentially elastic, not allowing us to capture the in-cycle degradation of the shear properties of a built-up column due to brace buckling and yielding.

Thus, for use in nonlinear models, the derived Timoshenko beam element should be transformed to an element with two end nodes that explicitly accounts for material nonlinearity under moment, shear and axial loads. One such option are two-node link elements that incorporate distinct, typically non-interacting, springs to account for each of the modes of relative deformation of its two ends. For example, in two dimensions, the two-node link element of OpenSees connects two nodes by three independent uniaxial springs to capture the axial, shear and rotational DOFs (Figure 7). In order to be equivalent to a beam element in the elastic region, it has to restore the same stiffness properties to the connected DOFs. Annex A describes the procedure to derive the springs' elastic axial, shear and rotational stiffnesses both for an Euler-Bernoulli and a Timoshenko beam element.

Considering inelastic response, the equivalent element axial force N_{eq} and bending moment M_{eq} for a frame comprising two uprights are related to pairs of axial forces of same and opposite direction, respectively, on the individual uprights (Figure 8a). Thus, failure occurs when the resulting axial force in any of the uprights exceeds the corresponding compressive or tensile strength, $N_{u,Rd}$, with compression being typically the governing situation:

$$N_{u,Rd} = \frac{N_{eq}}{2} + \frac{M_{eq}}{h_0}, \quad (6)$$

Figure 7: OpenSees' two-node link element for 2D analysis [23]. Nodes i and j are connected via three independent uniaxial springs to capture the axial, shear and rotational DOFs.

Figure 8: Transformation of member uprights' axial forces to stress resultants on the equivalent column, showing (a) a numerical example of an upright frame comprising two columns, and (b) the interaction between bending moment and axial force and the corresponding failure surface.

where h_0 is the horizontal distance between the uprights' center lines. From Eq. (6) it is evident that an interaction between the axial and rotational springs is required to determine failure (Figure 8b). However, due to the low stiffness of the roof truss connecting the upright frames, the shear lag between frames is of such magnitude that essentially the individual frames do not interact in developing appreciable global overturning resistance. Therefore, seismic forces do not influence N_{eq} , but only M_{eq} . As a result, N_{eq} can be considered to be constant as calculated from the gravity load analysis and decoupled axial/rotational springs can be employed. Thus Eq. (6) is solved for $M_{eq} = M_{eq,Rd}$, representing the maximum moment that the rotational spring can bear:

$$M_{eq,Rd} = h_0 \left(N_{u,Rd} - \frac{N_{eq}}{2} \right) \quad (7)$$

As upright buckling is an unstable failure mechanism, an abrupt drop to near-zero strength was employed for the post-buckling behaviour of the rotational spring. While Eq. (7) holds for upright frames with two uprights, it can straightforwardly be extended to the case of three equidistant uprights as $M_{eq,Rd} = 2h_0(N_{u,Rd} - N_{eq}/3)$. As the above simplifications assume no shear lag between adjacent uprights, extension to more than three is not recommended without care. Instead, one can combine multiple two- or three-member upright frames into one link element by summing their springs' stiffness, assuming negligible shear stiffness of the connecting roof truss (an assumption that introduces a small error as it will be seen later), the "100% shear lag" (Figure 9). This simplification procedure can be exploited to considerably reduce the complexity of the model, given the high level of commonality among the upright frames, with the associated penalties in considering spatial differences in the mass distribution and in the resolution of the analysis results.

Regarding the shear spring's nonlinear material law, a more sophisticated procedure was followed. A portion of the upright frame was isolated and tested under shear loading (Figure 10). Pinned supports were employed at the bottom nodes of the tested segment while rollers at the top ones. To account for the stiffness contribution of the adjacent (upper and lower) uprights, rotational springs were employed at the restrained nodes. The stiffness value of these springs cannot be derived analytically, but values between $EI/(4L)$ and $EI/(8L)$ (I and L the moment of inertia and the length of the adjacent upright, respectively) were adequately accurate. The horizontal and diagonal braces were simulated by force-based fiber elements with a corotational geometric transformation and a bow-type initial imperfection. The derived force-displacement curve was fitted by a piece-wise linear backbone, suitable for use with the OpenSees' Pinching4 material to represent each shear spring.

The force-deformation response of the shear spring under cyclic loading can be derived by performing a quasi-static analysis on the same test segment used for the backbone fit (Figure 10). A total of 10 cycles is performed, where the displacement increment is increased by 50% in each cycle. Figure 11 illustrates the "loading protocol" and the corresponding force-deformation curve of a test segment comprising 2 uprights. The hysteretic behaviour is characterized by significant pinching, due to the slenderness of the braces (typically allowed to be much higher than for conventional buildings), as also observed during experimental tests on concentrically-braced-frame specimens [27]. To decrease the work load, this quasi-static test was performed once and the same hysteretic properties were used for all the shear springs, assuming a similar cyclic behaviour.

Figure 9: Simplification stages for a multi-depth cross-aisle frame; assuming negligible shear stiffness of the roof truss, multiple two- or three- member upright frames can be substituted by a single link element.

Figure 10: Numerical shear testing of a triple-upright segment. Bow-type imperfections of $L/200$ are applied to the diagonals, while rotational springs stiffen the pin/roll end supports. The derived force-displacement curve is employed to define the shear spring of the link element.

Figure 11: Cycle shear testing of the upright frame segment showing, the loading protocol (left) and the calibrated force-deformation response of the shear spring (right).

Another important attribute that has to be discussed is the contribution of second-order effects. Elastic Timoshenko elements can easily consider geometric nonlinearities by employing a so-called P- Δ stiffness matrix, modified to account for shear deformations (see for instance, the standard beam element of SAP2000 [28]). On the other hand, a closed-form P- Δ matrix does not exist for a link element. As a remedy, OpenSees offers the ability to implicitly take into account the P- Δ effects, by introducing two “P-Delta moment contribution ratios”, namely μ_1 and μ_2 . Essentially these ratios increase the shear forces by $V_{P-\Delta}$ and bending moments by $M_{1,P-\Delta}$ and $M_{2,P-\Delta}$ on the connected nodes by a multiple of N/L , where N the axial force acting on the link element and L the length of the element. This is expressed in the following equations (dv the nodal relative displacement, perpendicular to the axis of the element):

$$V_{P-\Delta} = (1 - \mu_1 - \mu_2) \frac{N}{L} \quad (8)$$

$$M_{1,P-\Delta} = \mu_1 \frac{N \cdot dv}{L} \quad (9)$$

$$M_{2,P-\Delta} = \mu_2 \frac{N \cdot dv}{L} \quad (10)$$

Deriving a general analytical solution would require accounting for the effect of different bracing patterns, as well as different yielding mechanisms within the built-up column. Rather than attempting this approach, it is easier to perform the shear test (Figure 10) twice. The first time, the standard shear test is performed and the material law of the shear spring is derived. The second time, axial forces are assigned at the top nodes of the tested segment and the “P-Delta moment contribution ratios” of the link element are calibrated to match the corresponding force-displacement curve. The axial forces may assume the value of the gravity loads acting on the segment. Of course, then it becomes a question of whether the derived contribution factors depend on the magnitude of said forces. Our tests so far indicate that the contribution factors are largely insensitive to the magnitude of the axial forces, with the N/L term sufficiently capturing the effect of the different axial forces and the contribution factors characterizing the bracing configuration characteristics, as long as the yielding progression within the built-up column is not altered, e.g., the uprights do not buckle due to increased

axial force before the braces yield in tension. This is indeed the general case for our case study and it considerably simplifies the modeling effort. For the case at hand, $\mu_1 = \mu_2 = 0.20$ to 0.25 were found to be sufficient for all built-up column segments.

Following the simplification of the upright frames, the roof truss is then transformed to Timoshenko elements, assuming a linear elastic behaviour. Conceptually the roof can be viewed as a horizontal built-up column and therefore a similar procedure as the one for the upright frames can be followed. To alleviate the issue of the clear span being significantly different than the centreline length of the roof element, rigid offsets are employed, as illustrated in Figure 12.

Figure 12: Each roof beam element comprises two rigid parts at the two ends and one elastic in the middle, as its clear span is significantly different from the centreline length.

Finally, a structural detail that is worth mentioning is the grid formed by the rail and pallet beams in the multi-depth systems. This horizontal system affects the stiffness of the warehouse both in the cross- and the down-aisle direction (especially in the former) and it can only be captured by a 3D analysis. While the elastic properties of the equivalent uprights and pallet beams can be derived analytically, there is no closed-form solution for the equivalent rail beam. Thus, to consider the effect of the grid in the simplified model, a calibration procedure is followed. A small part of the ARSW is isolated both in the full and the simplified model, as shown in Figure 13. It was chosen to maintain the initial elastic length of the rail beam, by introducing rigid offsets and calibrating the torsional constant of the pallet beam until the first few modes of vibration of the simplified model match those of the full model. This procedure produces rapid results, as only a part of the full 3D model is considered.

Figure 13: Calibration procedure for the grid formed by the rail and pallet beams in multi-depth systems. A small part of the rack is considered (the black lines in the figure) and the torsional constant of the equivalent pallet beam is calibrated until the first few modes of vibration of the simplified model match those of the full model.

Case study 1: Elastic model of a multi-depth ARSW

Structure and Model Description

To illustrate the application of the proposed simplified model, a multi-depth ARSW is studied. It has been designed by professional engineers according to EN1993 [1], EN15512 [2] and EN16681[10] for a peak ground acceleration of $a_g = 0.3g$ and assuming a behaviour (or strength reduction) factor of $q = 1.5$. Despite being higher than 1.0, this value of q does not imply the presence of any appreciable ductility or capability for load redistribution in the structure, but only some inherent overstrength. Thus, a linear-elastic material model with geometric nonlinearities is suitable for full range assessment. The overall plan dimensions are 65.80 m x 71.50 m in the cross- and down-aisle direction, respectively, while the total height is about 25.60 m. Due to the high seismicity, three bracing towers are required along the down-aisle direction, placed at the two ends and the middle of the total length. Therefore, in the down-aisle direction 44 cross-aisle frames (Figure 14) are foreseen, comprising 38 “pallet frames” and 6 “tower frames”. The latter are connected in pairs by X-braces to form three concentrically braced towers that support the structure down-aisle.

Each cross-aisle frame is composed of 48 uprights, connected in pairs to form 24 “K-type” upright frames of 1.35 m width (Figure 15). “Tower” and “pallet” cross-aisle frames have similar geometry and bracing pattern, but the former ones use heavier sections. In both cases, their elements are cold-formed, with the uprights having Ω sections (Figure 16) and the K-braces channel sections. To optimize the design of the warehouse, profiles of lower thickness are used for the upper part of each upright frame. In the down-aisle direction, the pallet beams have a constant cross-section (with the exception of only a few that do not affect the stiffness of the structure) and are hooked to the uprights, creating semi-rigid connections (Figure 16). As for the bracing towers, reinforced $\Omega+U$ uprights are introduced up until the second load level, to withstand the increased axial forces arising from the seismic actions.

The cross-sectional properties for the main structural members are summarized in Table 2. The cross-section area of the diagonal braces of the upright frames was reduced to 10% to account for the reduced shear stiffness due to their bolted connection. Regarding the storage system, there are nine load levels, each comprising four storage cells of 13 unit-load capacity (Figure 15), thus each pallet frame supports up to 468 pallets. Load levels 1 to 2 are for 1000 kg pallets, 3 to 5 for 800 kg and 6 to 9 of 600 kg.

Figure 14: Down-aisle view of the multi-depth 3D Case Study 1. Each of the 44 vertical lines represents a single cross-aisle frame running perpendicularly to this figure. The 6 column-lines connected by X-braces correspond to heavy “tower” frames, while the remaining 38 are lighter “pallet” frames (units in meters).

Figure 15: Cross-aisle view of the multi-depth 3D Case Study 1, comprising 24 “K-type” upright frames and a connecting shallow roof truss (units in meters). Along the vertical there are 9 load levels, while along the horizontal direction, four storage cells are distinguished comprising 6 upright frames each.

Figure 16: Detail drawings for multi-depth Case Study 1, showing a: a reinforced upright $\Omega+U$ section, b: a standard upright Ω section and c: an upright-to-beam hooked connection.

Table 2: Cross-section properties of structural members (multi-depth, Case Study 1). Cross-section areas are rounded to the third digit while moments of inertia to the fifth.

Member	Section	A (mm ²)	I _y * (mm ⁴)	I _z ⁺ (mm ⁴)	I _t (mm ⁴)
Lower bracing upright (reinforced)	Ω+U	3500	9000000	6800000	24000
Lower bracing upright	Ω	1700	3900000	3800000	9000
Upper bracing upright	Ω	1100	2500000	2400000	2000
Lower pallet upright	Ω	1300	3000000	2900000	4000
Upper pallet upright	Ω	900	2000000	1900000	1000
Lower upright frame diagonal	C	500	150000	110000	500
Upper upright frame diagonal	C	300	340000	230000	500
Lower vertical bracing (floor-5 th level)	L	600	70000	200000	7000
Lower vertical bracing (6 th level-top)	L	300	120000	20000	1000

*I_y is along cross-aisle direction, ⁺I_z is along down-aisle direction

C = Channel section, I = I-shape section, L = angle section, Ω = Ω section, Ω+U = reinforced Ω section

Model Validation

Modal analysis is performed as an initial benchmark test, to check both the eigenvalues and the eigenmodes of the full versus the reduced model. The high commonality among the adjacent upright frames and the low shear stiffness of the roof truss enables the substitution of one to four upright frames (i.e., built-up columns) by a single equivalent “macro-column”, and thus each cross-aisle frame may be simplified to comprise only six such “macro-columns”. Both numerical models were realized using SAP2000 [28]. The full model, which captures all the structural details of the warehouse, requires approximately 647,000 DOFs and 200,000 Euler-Bernoulli beam elements making the pre- and post-processing extremely cumbersome. On the other hand, the simplified model with the six “macro-columns”, comprises 17,000 DOFs and 7,500 Timoshenko beam elements, leading to a reduction of 97.4%. Figure 17 illustrates the modes of vibration for both models.

As observed, some modes along the cross-aisle direction have sinusoidal shapes (i.e. diaphragm shearing), arising from the absence of a stiff roof that would act as a diaphragm. In the context of a modal response spectrum analysis (MRSA), an assumption of uniform spatial distribution of mass, and consequently seismic loading, would mean that such eigenmodes correspond to nearly zero modal participation factors, as typically estimated for the roof deformation. This can be shown by assuming N cross-aisle frames of m total mass each, moving in a sinusoidal pattern along the cross-aisle direction:

$$\begin{aligned} \Gamma_i &= \frac{L_i}{\hat{m}_i} = \frac{\varphi_i^T [M] \vec{r}}{\hat{m}_i} = \frac{\varphi_i^T [M] \vec{r}}{\hat{m}_i} \\ &= \frac{m \sum_{j=1}^N \sin(2\pi i(j-1)/(N-1)) \vec{r}}{\hat{m}_i} \approx \frac{m \left(\int_0^1 \sin(2\pi i x) dx \right) \vec{r}}{\hat{m}_i} = 0 \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

where $i \geq 1$, φ_i the eigenvector, \hat{m}_i the modal mass and Γ_i the modal participation factor of mode i and \vec{r} the influence vector (see Chopra 1996 [29]). In practice, though, minor asymmetries in the mass and/or stiffness distribution will typically result to small, non-zero values of Γ_i . As a result, the typical 90% mass participation is difficult to achieve, as it requires the addition of many such modes, leading to prohibitive time and storage costs. More worrisome is the fact that, despite their near-zero contribution to the roof deformation (where Γ_i and effective masses practically refer to), diaphragm-shearing modes have non-negligible contribution to local deformations and moments/forces on each frame. In other words, the missing 10% from a 90% effective mass inclusion may have significant consequences for some members. This highlights the potential for large errors at the local level when seismic design is based only on MRSA with modes selected according to their roof-level participation (see also Chopra 1996 [29]).

Figure 17: Modal analysis results of the 3D multi-depth Case Study 1 showing the dominant modes along the cross- and down-aisle direction as well as diaphragm shearing for the full model (left) and the simplified one (right).

Further to modal analysis, time-history analysis was conducted as a second benchmark test using a single 2D cross-aisle frame. The North-South component of the ChiChi 1999 event at Station CHY026 was selected from the PEER NGA database [30]. To demonstrate the progressive order (and resolution) reduction, four models were considered, namely the “full”

model (4863 DOFs), the “24 macro-columns” model (900 DOFs), the “12 macro-columns” model (396 DOFs) and finally the “6 macro-columns” (198 DOFs), as shown in Figure 9. All models incorporated geometric nonlinearities via P- Δ formulation and Rayleigh damping with viscous damping ratio of 3%. The maximum interstory drift profiles are shown in Figure 18, along with the relative error of each model. The “24 macro-columns” model showed excellent performance as it overestimated the maximum interstory drift only by 2%, while using 18.5% the DOFs of the full one. The other two models were less accurate which is attributed to the order reduction and to the assumption of “100% shear lag” during the combination of multiple upright frames. However, this may be a valid compromise as the complexity of the problem is reduced by orders of magnitude. Depending on numerical difficulty and the nature of the problem, one can choose the desiring level of fidelity or even combine different simplified approaches in the context of a multi-fidelity analysis.

Figure 18: Response history results for the 2D cross-aisle frame of Case Study 1, showing the peak interstory drift profiles for the four models (left) and the relative error of the maximum (over all stories) interstory drifts versus the DOFs of each model (right).

Fragility assessment

A set of 30 records is employed for conducting response history analyses. This has been selected to be consistent with the hazard at an intensity level corresponding to a 2%/50 years probability of exceedance in high seismicity European sites [31]. To reduce the computational demands, a multi-stripe analysis is performed [32] by scaling said records to three intensity levels, approximately corresponding to exceedance probabilities of 50%, 10%, and 2% in 50yrs. As intensity measure (IM) we employed the geometric mean of spectral acceleration from both horizontal components, $Sa(\bar{T})$, estimated at a mean period of $\bar{T} = 0.5(T_x + T_y)$, where T_x and T_y are the dominant modes along the cross- and down-aisle direction, respectively. The three intensity levels thus become $[0.5, 1.0, 1.5] \cdot Sa_d(\bar{T})$, where $Sa_d(\bar{T})$ is the 10% in 50 years value typically used in design.

The maximum interstory drift was adopted as the engineering demand parameter (EDP). Rayleigh damping was employed with a viscous damping ratio of 3% (per design specifications) assigned to periods 1.5s and 1.0s, due to the high concentration of multiple locally-

important modes within this range, as a consequence of having no rigid diaphragm. To account for global geometric nonlinearity effects, a P- Δ formulation was used in all beam-column elements. As a result of the introduced geometric nonlinearity, and despite the otherwise elastic model, a direct integration scheme was adopted, increasing the numerical effort for each time-history analysis. However, the simplified model was able to provide robustness, fast convergence and therefore significant time savings.

Figure 19 illustrates the results of the multi stripes analysis, highlighting the significant impact of the second-order effects, as the seismic response of the structure is highly nonlinear despite the absence of material nonlinearity. For illustrative purposes three indicative limit states are employed. They are defined by means of maximum interstory drift thresholds, namely Light Damage at 1%, Moderate Damage at 2% and Collapse Prevention at 4%. Non-simulated modes of failure were included in post-processing by checking for local member brittle failures (e.g., buckling of uprights, connection failure etc.), which are assumed to rapidly propagate to global collapse due to the lack of any meaningful force redistribution capability. Fragilities were derived by fitting the three stripes via the 5-parameter model of Jalayer and Cornell [32], comprising a lognormal distribution to capture collapse points (either from simulated or non-simulated modes), together with a power-law relationship [33] to model the conditional distribution of EDP given IM for non-collapse points. From Figure 19 it is evident that the derived Moderate Damage and Collapse Prevention fragility curves are almost identical, with the former having a probability of exceedance at the design level equal to 18% and the latter 16%. This confirms our intuition, i.e. the ARSWs designed according to current professional practice are optimized to the maximum, delivering the desired performance for design level intensities but not being able to extend into the beyond-design range with any confidence.

Figure 19: Multi stripes analysis for the multi-depth Case Study 1, showing the IM-EDP stripes for the three intensity levels (left), and the fragility curves for the three examined limit states (right).

Case study 2: Nonlinear model of a double-depth ARSW

Structure and Model Description

The ARSW double-depth frame under consideration was adopted from Caprili et al. [34], who designed it according to EN1993 [1] and EN1998 [35] for a peak ground acceleration of $a_g = 0.163g$ and assuming a behaviour (or strength reduction) factor of $q = 2$. It consists of 19 loading levels (“stories”), each with two exterior double-upright frames and four interior triple-upright frames (Figure 20a). Exterior frames can carry one pallet of 1000kg at each level, while interior frames carry two. This is a proof-of-concept design that does not follow current industry norms. It adopts a design approach more akin to conventional ductile concentric-braced frame buildings, where plasticity is concentrated in the bracing system

while the uprights remain elastic. Thus, compact hot-rolled sections are employed for the uprights (class 1 per EN1993-1, see Table 3), while capacity design is employed to ensure that no connections fail and tension braces yield before global or local buckling of uprights occurs.

Three numerical models of decreasing complexity were realized in OpenSees. A Rayleigh damping formulation was employed in all three, assigning a viscous damping ratio of 3% to the first and second eigenperiods of 1.03 and 0.41, respectively. Firstly, a “fiber model” (4758 elements, 3738 DOFs) was defined, where all structural members were simulated as force-based distributed-plasticity beam-column elements with fiber sections at 3 integration points. The Steel02 material of OpenSees was chosen with 0.5% strain-hardening and 10% fracture strain, representing the well-established Giuffr-Menegotto-Pinto model [36]. To account for flexural buckling, an imperfection equal to $L/200$ was introduced at mid-span of the diagonal braces. End releases were employed at the ends of the hinged diagonals and horizontals. As the fiber elements are computationally demanding, a “truss model” (1134 elements, 1086 DOFs) was also considered by substituting the distributed plasticity diagonal braces with lumped-plasticity nonlinear truss elements. The material law was derived from a uniaxial compression-tension numerical test of each diagonal, as shown in Figure 21. Clearly this is a conscious choice to ensure maximum compatibility and a fair comparison basis between the fiber and the truss model; in practice one could directly determine the truss backbone, e.g. as per ASCE 41-13 [13]. Considering the force-deformation response under cycle loading, the Pinching4 material of OpenSees was again used, calibrated in a same fashion as for the case of the shear spring of the link element (Figure 11). Only in-cycle degradation was incorporated in the trusses, neglecting any cyclic degradation effects. Finally, in the “link model” (252 elements, 234 DOFs), each square segment of an interior or exterior upright frame, measuring 2.5m and 1.25m high, respectively, is replaced by an equivalent two-node link element, while linear elastic Timoshenko beam elements are used for the truss roof (Figure 20b).

Figure 20: The cross-aisle view of the ARSW double-depth frame of Caprili et al [34], showing (a) the full model, and (b) the reduced-order one (units in meters).

Figure 21: Axial compression-tension numerical test for a distributed plasticity beam-column representation of diagonal brace. The derived force-deformation curve is employed to characterize the equivalent nonlinear truss element.

Table 3: Structural member cross-sections and steel grade for interior and exterior upright frames (Case 2). Per EN1993 [1], steel grade Sxxx has a characteristic yield strength of xxx MPa.

Height (m)	Uprights (both)	Diagonal (exterior)	Diagonal (interior)	Horizontal (both)
0.0–2.3	RHS* (S355) 120x80x10	L ⁺ (S355) 40x40x5	L (S355) 40x40x5	DC ⁺⁺ (S355) 80x50x3
2.3–4.8	RHS (S355) 120x80x10	L (S275) 40x40x4	RHS (S355) 30x30x2.5	DC (S355) 80x50x3
4.8–9.8	RHS (S355) 120x80x6	L (S275) 40x40x4	RHS (S355) 30x30x2.5	DC (S355) 80x50x3
9.8–13.6	RHS (S355) 120x80x4	L (S275) 35x35x4	RHS (S275) 30x30x2.5	DC (S355) 80x50x3
13.6–23.2	RHS (S355) 120x80x4	L (S235) 30x30x4	RHS (S235) 30x30x2	DC (S355) 80x50x3

*RHS = Rectangular Hollow Section, ⁺L = Angle Section, ⁺⁺DC = Double-Channel Section

Model Validation

Static pushover analysis (SPO) was conducted to verify the suitability of the proposed models in the inelastic region. A first-mode-like triangular load distribution was adopted and the displacement of the roof was monitored up until 4.0% interstorey drift was achieved. Figure 22 illustrates the capacity curves for the three models under consideration, signifying the ability of the frugal link model to produce accurate results even for large inelastic deformations.

Figure 22: Capacity curves for the three numerical models of Case Study 2, showing the base shear versus the roof displacement (left), and versus the maximum interstory drift (right).

For further verification a series of nonlinear response history analyses was performed using the same ground motion record as for the Case Study 1 (ChiChi 1999, Station CHY026 [30]). Four levels of intensity were employed, at scale factors of 0.89, 1.00, 2.41 and 4.44 to show progressive levels of damage.

Figure 23 illustrates the maximum drift profiles for each record scale, showing a good correspondance among the three numerical models. At the third scaling level, where the highest divergence was found, the link model predicted a maximum interstory drift equal to 0.50% vis-à-vis 0.55% of the fiber, showing a 10% underestimation. However, this relative difference is not consistent, as the link model sometimes overestimates and others times underestimates the maximum interstory drift, depending on the record employed. Thus, it is more akin to random error (i.e. noise) rather than bias, and it could thus be treated by increasing the dispersion of the predicted response to account for modelling uncertainty (see also FEMA P-58 [37]). Still, its magnitude is negligible vis-à-vis the 30% – 40% dispersion due to record-to-record variability, allowing us to safely disregard it. Finally, considering performance gains, each time-history analysis requires approximately 30 seconds for the link model, 60 minutes for the truss model and the 90 minutes for the fiber model on an Intel i5 3.40 GHz desktop. These time-savings are expected to be even greater for the case of multi-depth ARSWs (as the number of upright frames is increased) or for the obvious case of three-dimensional analyses.

Figure 23: Maximum inter-story drift profile for the three numerical models of Case Study 2 (full, truss and link model). Four record scales were considered corresponding scale factors of 0.89, 1.00, 2.41 and 4.44.

Fragility assessment

Offering a detailed view of demand at each IM level, Incremental Dynamic Analysis (IDA [38]) is adopted to conduct fragility assessment. Due to their propensity for numerical instabilities in the post-yield region and the prohibitive computational time required, models that comprise fiber elements (i.e., both the “fiber” and the “truss” models) were not considered; instead the “link” model allowed us to perform the analysis within only 2-3 hours on an Intel i5 3.40 GHz desktop. The same set of 30 records [31] employed for Case Study 1 is also

used here. The maximum interstory drift was adopted as the EDP and the 5%-damped first-mode spectral acceleration as the IM.

Figure 24a and Figure 24b present the IDA curves and the 16%, 50%, 84% fractiles, respectively, highlighting the significant record-to-record variability, easily eclipsing the much lower modeling uncertainty. The IDA curves indicate the presence of considerable ductility, thanks to the capacity design rules employed. As already mentioned, this is atypical of actual ARSW structures, yet highly indicative of the seismic performance gains realized by adopting ductile design standards. Fragility curves corresponding to an exceedance of 1%, 2% and 4% maximum interstory drift, akin to a Light Damage, Moderate Damage and Collapse Prevention limit-states, respectively, are illustrated in Figure 25. The resulting median value of spectral acceleration is 1.0g, whereas the design value is only 0.26g, showing excellent performance. Actually, at the design level acceleration there is practically a zero probability of limit-state exceedance, compared to the 17% probability derived for Case Study 1. Still, such performance gains come at a substantial cost of material, employing hot-rolled rather than cold-formed members, together with stronger connections, making this a difficult choice.

Figure 24: IDA analysis results for the link model of Case Study 2, showing the individual IDA curves of each record (left), and the corresponding 16%, 50% and 84% fractiles (right).

Figure 25: Fragility curves for Light Damage, Moderate Damage and Collapse Prevention limit states of Case Study 2.

Conclusions

A reduced-order modelling approach has been presented for the seismic analysis of ARSWs. It is based on the well-established substitution of built-up columns and truss beams with

equivalent Timoshenko beam elements, reducing the size of the numerical problem by orders of magnitude. The proposed simplified model goes one step beyond by providing the ability for inelastic static and dynamic simulations with negligible loss of accuracy. This is achieved with the use of link elements that can capture the shear, axial and rotational stiffness degradation of the substituted upright frames. As the evaluation of ARSWs' seismic behaviour is an on-going research process, the proposed simplified model can suitably fit in the context of performance-based assessment and design, where low complexity without loss of fidelity is a primary goal.

Appendix A. Spring stiffnesses of two-node link element

Given L , E , A and I the elastic properties of an Euler Bernoulli beam element, a triplet K_a , K_s and K_r resembling springs' linear stiffnesses has to be determined. In the consolidated system (Figure A.1), an axial nodal displacement δ_a leads to an equal axial spring-displacement $\delta_{a,spring} = \delta_a$, a potential energy U and axial force N related as:

$$U = \frac{1}{2} K_a \delta_a^2 \Rightarrow K_a \delta_a = \frac{\partial U}{\partial \delta_a} = N = \frac{EA}{L} \Rightarrow K_a = \frac{EA}{L} \quad (A.1)$$

Similarly, a transversal nodal displacement δ_s leads to a shear force F :

$$U = \frac{1}{2} K_s \delta_s^2 \Rightarrow K_s \delta_s = \frac{\partial U}{\partial \delta_s} = F = \frac{12EI}{L^3} \Rightarrow K_{s,EB} = \frac{12EI}{L^3} \quad (A.2)$$

On the other hand, a nodal rotation φ excites a coupled behaviour between the shear and rotational spring, producing both a shear displacement δ and rotation a φ (Figure A.1). For small displacements, it can easily be shown that $\delta = \varphi L/2$ holds, leading to:

$$U = \frac{1}{2} K_s \delta^2 + \frac{1}{2} K_r \varphi^2 \Rightarrow K_s \frac{L^2}{4} \varphi + K_r \varphi = \frac{\partial U}{\partial \varphi} = \frac{4EI}{L} \Rightarrow K_r = \frac{EI}{L} \quad (A.3)$$

Same procedure can be followed for the case of a Timoshenko beam element with the difference that Eq. (A.2) is transformed to account for a potential shear deformation:

$$K_{s,T} = \frac{12EI}{(1+\Phi)L^3}, \quad \Phi = \frac{12EI}{L^2 GA_s} \quad (A.4)$$

Figure A1: Unit nodal displacement/rotation for the derivation of springs' elastic stiffnesses (axial, shear and rotational spring).

Data availability statement

Some or all data, models, or code that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request: Case Study 2 models, data and all respective code.

Some or all data, models, or code generated or used during the study are proprietary or confidential in nature and may only be provided with restrictions: Case Study 1 models and data.

Acknowledgements

This research is co-financed by Greece and the European Union (European Social Fund-ESF) through the Operational Programme «Human Resources Development, Education and Lifelong Learning» in the context of the project “Strengthening Human Resources Research Potential via Doctorate Research” (MIS-5000432), implemented by the State Scholarships Foundation (IKY). Moreover, the authors acknowledge the support of the European Commission through the Research Fund for Coal and Steel (RFCS) Project STEELWAR, under Grant Agreement Number 754102.

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